

ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING PROCESSES FOR HIGHLY SKILLED FOOTBALLERS FOR COMPETITIONS

Jengis Turdimuratov

Islambek Auezov

Berdaq Karakalpak State University, Uzbekistan, Nukus city.

E-mail: ayqiz67@mail.ru

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Abstract. *The article examines the current state of improving the organization of the training process for footballers, defines the theoretical foundations of the training process for highly qualified footballers at the initial training stage, and also develops training exercises that simulate game situations at different stages.*

Keywords: *organization; training; process; Football, football players.*

Entry. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2018 No. PP-3610 "On measures to further develop football" creates great opportunities for the country's physical culture and sports, in particular, football and specialists in this field. In pursuance of this resolution, promising changes are being implemented in the football of our republic. Modern methods of improving the special physical, technical and tactical training of highly skilled footballers, considered in the master's dissertation, are one of the important tasks in their preparation for competitions. The high sports skills of highly skilled footballers ensure their success in competitions.

Purpose and objectives. The processes of achieving success in competitions with the improvement of technical and tactical skills, special physical training of highly skilled footballers in the team of Karakalpak State University were studied.

The scientific novelty of the research. The results of the master's dissertation can be used to further improve the process of preparing highly qualified athletes for sports competitions, as well as to ensure continuous achievement of results in sports competitions.

The main questions and hypotheses of the article.

- Analysis of the results of competitive activity of highly qualified and young footballers of Uzbekistan;

- Analysis of the results of competitive activity of highly qualified foreign players;

- Factors affecting the speed of technical and tactical actions.

Characteristics of the methodology used in the study. The article extensively utilizes methods of literature analysis, pedagogical control, and experiment, mathematical and statistical analysis of results, medical and biological, as well as psychological control of scientific research. At the same time, Internet materials were used in the writing of the master's dissertation.

The theoretical and practical significance of the research results. The results of the study will be applied in practice to the training exercises of the Karakalpak State University. As a result, it is envisaged to ensure the success of football players in sports competitions. General and special sports training exercises of highly skilled footballers were studied.

As we live in an era when physical culture and sports have become an important factor in the development of the social sphere in our country, government decisions aimed at supporting this sphere are very important. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2018 N. PP-3610 "On measures for the further development of football" created great opportunities for specialists in the field of physical culture and sports, in particular, domestic football. The implementation of this decree will lead to promising changes in local football.

Particular attention is paid to the work related to the training of footballers, the improvement of training systems and ensuring their results.

In football, as in other sports, two teams that strive to win will meet. The struggle for victory requires very strong physical, intellectual and endurance qualities from athletes. Only footballers who have fully mastered their skills can ensure success in individual wrestling with an equal opponent.

During the game, when they own the ball, each team will have to perform many attacking movements using different means and methods of wrestling. Therefore, the most important thing in tactics is to ensure the achievement of the goal, to know the specific means of conducting offensive and defensive actions, methods and the ability to widely use their capabilities in attack - all of this testifies to the tactical maturity of its special athletes, as well as the entire team. The training of young athletes involves a multi-year training process, all components of which depend on the level of development of successful sportsmanship - the development of physical qualities, the improvement of technical and psychological readiness of each athlete. However, tactical training is the most important in sports, especially in football.

Group tactical actions in sports games are one of the most important components for achieving positive results, especially in highly skilled teams. This is evidenced by the fact that many famous practicing coaches (V.A. Arkadev; O.R. Bazelevich; K.L. Beskov; A.Ya. Gomelsky; G.D. Kachalin; I.A. Koshbakhtiev; V.V. Lombonovsky; V.A. Maslov; M.I. Yakushin) confirms.

M.A. Godik, analyzing the large-scale football competitions of recent years with his staff, concluded that in modern football, the importance of conducting a team game based on the successful combination of high individual qualities of each player in the team, such as expanding the universal capabilities of players, increases. According to the opinions expressed, the universalization of football players is becoming increasingly widespread. At the same time, athletes who are able to play correctly on the spot, who will eventually complete counterattacks such as defense at any place on the field, are considered universal, in addition, it is important to be able to maintain a high pace from the beginning to the end of the game.

Conclusion. In the process of preparing a master's dissertation, the processes of improving the technical and tactical skills, as well as developing special physical qualities of highly qualified football players of the football and sports club of Karakalpak State University were studied.

The training process of highly skilled footballers, the daily routine, as well as the processes of sports training were analyzed. Training sessions are organized twice a day during the day and in the evening. Training sessions are preparatory exercises in which athletes develop technical and tactical skills, as well as strength, endurance, flexibility, speed, and agility.

Exercises organized in the improvement groups are carried out in order to see the practical and theoretical, as well as moral and endurance readiness of football players for planned sports competitions.

Football training sessions are divided into preparatory, competitive and transitional periods.

During the preparatory period, it is necessary to organize the technical, tactical and physical training of football players for the next competitions. During the competition, the footballers demonstrate their technical and tactical readiness, physical qualities, and demonstrate their moral and ethical qualities for victory.

During the transition period, measures will be taken to eliminate the physical exertion, intellectual and nervous fatigue received by football players during competitions. At the same time, athletes actively rest with activities such as active games, trips, tourism, water procedures.

Sometimes passive breathing is prescribed, such as taking medicines and medicines, bed, peace and listening to music, diet, massage, and sauna.

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